

ADVANCED PHOTONIC SUBSYSTEMS TO IMPLEMENT RECONFIGURABLE, FAULT-TOLERANT AVIONICS

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Abstract¹

Existing and emerging combat, support, and commercial aircraft and rotorcraft will continue to incorporate new sensors, data processors, and related systems that will make the complex, mostly federated avionics systems of the 70's through 90's look like antiques. As the data processing, multi-sensor fusion, and automatic operations continue to burden the conventional avionics infrastructures, new and innovative architectures and subsystems will be needed to meet the high-bandwidth, low-latency, and other criteria of future avionics systems. Implicit in such future systems will be the requirement for fault-tolerance and reconfiguration in the presence of faults.

The tremendous growth in the telecommunications infrastructure has led to a series of technologies and devices that provide the basis for unique subsystems that can implement such advanced, reconfigurable, fault-tolerant avionics systems. At Systran Federal Corp., we are developing two photonic subsystems that can realize the vision of such avionics systems. These subsystems are called the JANUS fault-tolerant communications device and the AEGLE photonic switching system. JANUS is a specialized Fibre-Channel interface that offers 2 Gigabits/sec of data movement across multiple interfaces. AEGLE is a photonic switching system that incorporates emerging switching devices at its core.

This paper provides our vision for the ROSAA (Reconfigurable Open-Systems Avionics Architecture) and details of the JANUS and

AEGLE prototype subsystems we are developing to achieve this vision.

AATD Mission and ROSA Activities

The Aviation Applied Technology Directorate (AATD), located at Ft. Eustis, Virginia, is a major component of the US Army Aviation and Missile Command's Research, Development, and Engineering Center. It is responsible for developing, demonstrating, and transitioning critical technologies to current, developmental, and future air-mobile platforms. AATD and its predecessor organizations have earned a venerable reputation through more than 50 years of applied research and advanced technology development aimed primarily at combat rotorcraft. Today, the organization focuses its research efforts on new propulsion systems and drive trains, susceptibility reduction and survivability enhancements, advanced structures and materials, and integrated sensors, weapons, and C4I (command, control, communications, computers, and intelligence). In addition to its research mission, the organization provides engineering and rapid prototyping support to the Aviation Program Executive Office (i.e., the platform Program Managers) and to special mission users.

The AATD Systems Integration Division evaluates new concepts related to signature management and reduction, weapons integration and fire control, situation awareness, aircrew information and decision aiding, the teaming of manned and unmanned vehicles, and advanced avionics architectures, functions, components, and subsystems. AATD is interested in open systems specifications, standards, and interfaces and in using commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) electronics on advanced rotorcraft primarily as a means of reducing rotorcraft acquisition and operations and support costs. Justification for this interest is seen in Figure 1 [1] which indicates that rotorcraft

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avionics acquisition cost as a function of unit flyaway cost has risen over time from about 5-10% during the 1960s to about 55% today, a trend Army Aviation believes it must reverse.

However, the Army is well aware of the tremendous advantages that advanced sensors, weapons, fire control, vehicle management systems, and other advanced processing functions provide even as it addresses its avionics cost problems. Clearly, aviation must capture and employ the processing performance gains made available by COTS electronics and create upgrade paths for flight, safety, and mission critical processing. Conventional standards, such as Mil-Std-1553 and others, will not be sufficient to perform the required tasks. Bandwidth, memory, and throughput requirements have greatly exceeded their capacities. For example, the RAH-66 Comanche reconnaissance/attack helicopter has known bus bandwidth requirements for 527.2 Megabits/sec to support its digital 2nd generation pilotage FLIR, 147.5 Megabits/sec to support its digital helmet display interface, and for 7 Megabits/sec to support digital map data access. Radar and sensor fusion estimates are on the order of 1-2 Gigabits/sec, and future digital sensor and display requirements are expected to exceed 2 Gigabits/sec. Its total mission avionics bandwidth requirement is estimated at 2 to 3 Gigabits/sec when the aircraft goes to production in 2006 [2].

Moreover, future Army Aviation mission processing capabilities and functions include manned/unmanned teaming; video transmission, reception, and manipulation; real-time synthetic 3D visualization; cognitive decision aiding; and advanced survivability and will drive bandwidth and throughput requirements such that they may approach those of the Joint Strike Fighter (see Figure 2 [3]).

As Army Aviation moves to COTS and open systems-based processing environments, it is important that we not sacrifice reliability. Reconfigurable systems are seen as a means achieving high levels of reliability and battle damage tolerance. In addition, there is some thinking that aviation may move to distributed

processing infrastructures characterized by reconfigurable processing when systems fail or are damaged. Technologies, such as those being pursued in the Reconfigurable Open Systems Avionics Architecture (ROSAA) project, are key to achieving the architectural, cost, performance, reliability, and battle damage goals envisioned by the Army for its future rotorcraft. But, what are the reliability levels we should strive to achieve? Figure 3 [4] compares top-level reliability figures for flight critical systems as defined by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and by the Department of Defense (rotorcraft requirements per Mil-F-9490).

Avionics affordability, performance, growth, and reliability are extremely important for the Army's current and future rotorcraft fleet. Tradeoffs are not only possible, but likely. Furthermore, how do we design systems for optimum life cycle cost? And, what are the complications to these designs as we move to higher levels of functional integration (such as that described by ARINC-653)? Figure 4 [5] illustrates the notional relationship between reliability and cost and indicates that life cycle cost can be optimized at some less than optimum reliability level.

Parts obsolescence problems also affect affordability, performance, growth and reliability. Although, obsolescence is analyzed before avionics production begins, because aircraft purchases are frequently made in blocks, exposure always exists in the long term. Partial solutions exist at different levels in the design. In the commercial computer market place, the product cycle is so short that reliance upon those parts can create a worse parts obsolescence problem than already exists for military or industrial parts based designs. The best defense against parts obsolescence is to use standard interfaces such that an equivalent part or module can be inserted with minimal impact on other circuits. The software can also be made tolerant of new processors using common Application Program Interfaces (APIs). Using industrial standard backplane interfaces not only means the interface chips are less expensive but the potential exists for plug and play of designs from different suppliers or upgraded designs.

Figure 1. The Increasing Nature of Rotorcraft Avionics Cost [1]

JSF Estimates – Total Bandwidth Estimate = 5 to 20 Gbps		
Function	Network Data Rate (per channel)	Digital Signal Processing Throughput
Synthetic Aperture Radar / MTI	500 – 1000 Mbps	10 – 15 GFLOPS
Space / Time Adaptive Processing	N/A	10 – 15 GFLOPS
EO Sensing	250 Mbps	10 – 100 GOPS
Electronic Warfare	1000 – 3000 Mbps	5 – 10 GFLOPS
Cockpit Video	500 – 1000 Mbps	500 – 1000 MFLOPS

Figure 2. Joint Strike Fighter Bandwidth Estimates [3]

Mission Avionics and Vehicle Management Systems are commonly separate in military aircraft	
Bandwidth, Throughput, and Weight drive Mission Systems	Fault Tolerance and Reliability drive Vehicle Management Systems
Mbit/sec to Gbit/sec bandwidth requirements	FAR 25.1309: Probability of failure for flight critical system $1E-8$ per flight hour
MTBF ~ 70 hours for complex mission systems	MIL-F-9490: Probability of failure resulting in loss of aircraft $25E-7$ per flight hour
Fault detection, isolation, and repair are critical (0.98 – 0.99; 1.25 hr MTTR)	Multiply redundant (triplex or quadruplex not uncommon)
Mission abort rates ~ 1 percent	Must be deterministic
	Bandwidth and performance are not driving factors (kbit/sec rates acceptable for many applications)

Figure 3. Mission Avionics and Vehicle Management Systems Reliability Requirements Comparison [4]

Figure 4. The Optimum Life Cycle Cost is a Function of Reliability [5]

Benefits & Challenges of Avionics Integration

Avionics integration is pursued for two primary reasons. Functional integration enables the merging of information for the purpose of improving crewmember, aircraft, and mission performance.² It is achieved using data buses to communicate information to system processing centers, fusion of information from various sources, and, for manned aircraft, the presentation of all task relevant information on multifunction displays. Physical integration has the objective of increasing implementation efficiency, lowering cost and system overhead through the use of shared assets (i.e., computers, data buses), and increasing reliability through redundant or reconfigurable assets.

Avionics architectures are comprised of interfaces, function partitioning, and topology. Topology is most readily analyzed as it results from the reliability and redundancy requirements and the type of network being applied. Optimizing function assignment to resource is a larger problem to the integrator. Avionics vendors and the development labs work against integration by developing stand-alone subsystems.

To best address the near term and future needs of rotorcraft, changes are needed to standardize new system interfaces. New commercial standards are needed, particularly at three interfaces; first, at the

system level, a new high performance network; second, at the module (circuit card) level, a standard backplane, and; third, at the application software to processor hardware interface.

The ROSA Project

Concurrently as AATD and Systran Federal Corporation conduct ROSAA, AATD and the Boeing Company are pursuing the Rotorcraft Open Systems Avionics (ROSA) project.² ROSA is evaluating the degree to which open systems specifications, standards, and interfaces and COTS electronics can be used to satisfy the current, near-term, and projected future mission avionics processing requirements for the Army's most advanced combat rotorcraft systems. Therefore, ROSA is promoting an enterprise solution and is taking a comprehensive look at core processing network operational and technical requirements. The project is investigating the performance, reliability, fault tolerance, and cost of key components through a series of laboratory demonstrations and engineering application studies. The project seeks reductions in system cost, space, and weight while enabling the integration of new and advanced processing functions. ROSA will

² When SFC coined the term ROSAA (double A), we were unaware of the other program called ROSA (single A).

design, fabricate, and evaluate an advanced open avionics system architecture employing commercial standards and components. It will demonstrate technologies needed to support Army production aircraft programs and which will still be valuable standards well into the future.

ROSA is capitalizing and building on the efforts of the Boeing "Boldstroke" project which has, for several years now, pursued the objective of an enterprise solution with respect to avionics development to reduce the cost of the Boeing military aviation product line. Boldstroke addresses the common avionics requirements of the AH-64, RAH-66, F-15, F-18, AV-8B, C-17, JSF and several other aircraft and has resulted in numerous trade studies and advanced designs.

Boldstroke has spawned cooperative developments with the Air Force, Navy, and Marine corps for the AV-8B, F-15, and F-18. The Open System Core Avionics Requirements (OSCAR) project replaced the AV-8B's core computers with COTS based, VME64, 6U form factor computers and a high speed Fibre Channel bus. Boeing is also nearing completion on two COSSI (Commercial Operational & Support Savings Initiative) contracts for the F-15 and F-18. Key functions of the F-15 OFP (operational flight program) were re-hosted into an Advanced Display Core Processor (ADCP)

and a new AMLCD was flight-tested. As a COSSI project, the F-18 will also receive a new Advanced Mission Computer and Displays (AMCD). ROSA is similar in nature to these projects in that selected subsets of the Apache Longbow and Comanche OFP will be hosted and operated in a commercial-based, open processing environment.

Emerging Preferred Standards

ROSA is defining and promoting a set of preferred standards and coordinating these extensively with Government and industry. These standards are documented in the ROSA Rotorcraft Technical Architecture (RTA), which has been reviewed by approximately 100 organizations. AATD is also working with the Weapon Systems Technical Architecture Working Group (WSTAWG) and the Army Systems Engineering Office to extract particular standards from the RTA and nominate them for inclusion in the Joint Technical Architecture - Army (JTA-A). Figure 5 depicts the RTA top-level standards. Elements of this architecture are applicable to upgrades or life cycle cost reduction efforts for the Army's manned rotorcraft (AH-64, RAH-66, CH-47, and UH-60) and it is noteworthy that Apache Longbow and Comanche are already planning to use some of these standards.

Figure 5. Emerging ROSA Preferred Standards

The ROSAA SBIR

In the Summer of 1999, Systran Federal Corporation (SFC) responded to a AATD-issued Phase I SBIR (Small Business Innovation Research) program with a proposal entitled ROSAA (Reconfigurable, Open Systems Avionics Architecture). The keystone of this proposal was the top-level architecture illustrated in Figure 6. This figure illustrates the sensors, effectors, and displays used within rotorcraft (or other platforms) all interconnected with a set of processing clusters, switches, and perhaps even a replicated shared-memory network. While some time in this Phase I program was spent reviewing and formulating concepts for fault-tolerant and reconfigurable

software elements of such an overall architecture, we rapidly focused our efforts on formulating specific products that would, perhaps, be beneficial to those organizations conducting the larger ROSA program.

After a few months of in-house meeting, market research, and emerging technology reviews, we prepared concepts for two new products that would form the basis for the Phase II (prototype development) portion of the SBIR. These products included the low-risk JANUS fault tolerant communications device and the leading edge AEGLE photonic switching system.

The following sections provide highlights of these two products, now in Phase II prototyping at SFC.

Figure 6. Top-Level ROSAA Architecture

Telecommunications Technology Pull

It is important to realize that affordable technology leadership no longer resides within the Department of Defense. While this may not be news to the large number of DASC attendees, it is perhaps a concept foreign to our contracting and procurement organizations, which exert significant bottom-line cost constraints on the systems we conceptualize and hope to field. This situation is the result of the last 20 years or so of explosive growth in the PC and telecommunications markets. Now, of course,

military organizations and their contractors must draw from devices and standards that are common within these other markets, so that we can have some hope of finding sources of devices that can be utilized within our subsystems and systems.

In the ROSAA program, we are drawing upon two such technologies – Fiber Channel high bandwidth data communications and the more recent technology developments in photonic switching devices. How these technologies intersect with the ROSAA products will become obvious in the next sections of this paper.

Fault Tolerant Communications Device -- JANUS

In order to implement the ROSAA architecture (previously illustrated in Figure 6) we recommended the use of a smart, multiple-port Fibre Channel communications interface. Our design activities have led to the formulation of the 6U VME Fibre Channel Host Bus Interface illustrated in Figure 7. The salient features of this HBA include:

- Two, independent 1 or 2 Gbps ANSI std Fiber Channel protocol engines (a)
- Two independent switching systems (b)
- Four independent transceivers (c)
- An on-board processor running fault-tolerant and system reconfiguration software (d)
- Initial VME bus (e)
- Stiffener for rugged environments (f)

Figure 7. JANUS Board Layout (April 2001)

The JANUS software architecture is illustrated in Figure 8, and includes:

- Universe II IP Driver -- A system level device driver that encapsulates the hardware functionality of the Tundra Universe II VME-PCI bridge chip. Additional functionality ties this device into the operating system's TCP/IP stack, allowing IP communication over the VME bus. (g)
- TCP/IP Stack -- Provided and managed by the operating system, the TCP/IP stack controls the routing of TCP/IP traffic through the system. (h)
- Telnet Control Shell -- Written as a simple command line application, operable via a telnet login, this shell provides a simple user interface that allows a user to configure the fault redundant switching hardware of the JANUS device. (i)
- Serial Control Shell -- The serial control shell works similar to the telnet control shell, however runs over serial port instead of TCP/IP. Additional functionality is included in this application to allow

configuring of the device TCP/IP and VME addresses at installation time. (j)

- Fibre Channel Driver -- A system level device driver for controlling the dual Fiber Channel interfaces. This code is primarily an FX200 device driver for the Linux operating system with some additional logic for handling certain fault conditions specific to the JANUS device. (k)
- Path Control API -- Written as a dynamic library module, the path control API provides an application level programmers interface for the path control driver. An additional TCP/IP interface allows path control via IP. (l)
- Path Control Driver -- A system level device driver that encapsulates the hardware functionality of the Janus fault redundant switch mechanism. (m)

We selected JANUS as the code name for this new product. Just as JANUS, the Roman god who was the “guardian of gates and doors”, the JANUS fault tolerant communications device we are developing will be able to monitor the status of the various links it is connected to, and to rapidly reconfigure itself whenever external link faults or on-board device faults occur, and maintain ongoing communications between its processor cluster and other communication sources and sinks within the overall avionics suite.

The use of Fibre Channel communications mechanisms within avionics systems has been an emerging trend during the last few years. Specific details about the benefits of Fibre Channel within this operational domain can be found in [6].

Figure 8. JANUS Software Architecture

Photonic Switching System – AEGLE

The second product we are developing in the ROSAA Phase II program is a photonic switching system. This will initially be an 8 x 8 crosspoint switching system based upon a MEMS (Miniature Electro Mechanical System) switching device from OMM (Optical Micro Machines), San Diego, CA. While OMM has developed and is delivering both 2-D and 3-D photonic switching systems for the

telecommunications infrastructure markets, our switching system is the first time that their device has been employed in an aerospace avionics application.

The OMM device is shown in Figure 9. This device uses two, eight-fiber ribbons for input and output, with electrical control of the switches crosspoints (which are miniature mirrors).

An example of how this switch operates is provided in Figure 10.

In this 4 x 4 crosspoint switch example, fibers 1 , 2, 3, and D are providing input photon streams. Two of the 16 MEMS mirrors have been placed into the “up” or “1” state, thereby directing input stream 3 to output port C and input stream D to output port 4.

Keep in mind that, unlike conventional electrical crosspoint switches (e.g., Vitesse part VSC835), these photonic switching devices are bi-directional, permitting input photon streams to enter the MEMS crosspoint matrix from either direction.

Figure 9. Optical Micro Machines 8x8 photonic switching device

Figure 10. Photonic Switching via MEMS Mirrors [7]

Figure 11 illustrates our initial physical design for the JANUS. We are able to incorporate an 8x8 OMM photonic switching device on a typical 6U

VME board. This allows us room for some other functionality (still in R&D) and careful management of the fiber ribbon cables. Ribbon

connectors can be affixed to the front or rear panel, depending upon the needs of the user. In ancient Greek mythology, AEGLE was the god of dazzling light. In a similar manner, the AEGLE photonic switching systems will rapidly switch

multiple photon streams of coherent laser/LED light, providing high bandwidth communications between elements of emerging and future avionics systems.

Figure 11. AEGLE Preliminary Layout (June 2001)

Typical ROSAA Network

The JANUS and AEGLE 6U VME boards provide the systems integrator with broad flexibility in system implementation options.

Figure 12 illustrates a typical network, in this case composed of three processor clusters, each with a single JANUS fault tolerant communications device installed³. These three processor clusters are interconnected via two AEGLE 8x8 photonic switches. Data is flowing, using the Fiber Channel protocol, at bandwidths exceeding 1Gbps pairs of fiber optic filaments.

What happens when a fault occurs, through either combat damage or other types of component

³ The network illustration in Figure 12 was simplified by the intentional withholding of FO filaments between the three other transceivers on the individual JANUS boards.

failures?

Figure 13 illustrates one possible method for reconfiguration of this ROSAA network. The discussion below is keyed to the numbers in the figure.

- (1) At $t=t_0$, one or both of the fiber optic links is severed.
- (2) The on-board processor and embedded software detects this loss of signal.
- (3) Signals are re-routed through transceiver #2, previously connected as shown through AEGLE#1 to JANUS #2, transceiver 1B.
- (4) Data movement continues through JANUS #1
- (5) Data movement continues through JANUS #2
- (6) At $t=t_{later}$, a malfunction is detected in this Fibre Channel engine.
- (7) The on-board processor and embedded software detects this malfunction

(8) Signals are rerouted through the alternate Fibre Channel engine

(9) Data movement continues between JANUS #3 and JANUS #2 (5).

Figure 12. JANUS And AEGLE Provide Significant Flexibility To The Systems Integrator

Figure 13. One Possible Reconfiguration In The Presence Of Faults

Summary

The mission of AATD and the challenges it faces have been defined. The ROSA response to these challenges has been introduced. Two unique ROSAA products in development to support this response have been described.

Of course, the real payoffs to the product concepts described in this paper will not be known until these products are integrated into complete avionics systems and then subjected to laboratory and flight tests. We are pleased to report that we (SFC and AATD) are collaborating with Boeing, through its Boldstroke avionics laboratory, for beta testing of these products as part of its ROSA Comanche demonstration, currently scheduled for the March/April 2002 timeframe.

Additional Information

Additional information about the Fibre Channel protocol, standards, working groups, and related issues can be obtained from the Fibre Channel Industry Association (FCIA) at <http://www.fibrechannel.org/>

Information about the ROSAA products in development – JANUS and AEGLE – is available from gvalentino@systranfederal.com.

Information about the ROSA program and AATD's activities can be obtained from djohnson@aatd.eustis.army.mil.

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